

**FACTORS AFFECTING THE ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION
OF STUDENTS AT BS LEVEL AT DISTRICT
BANNU**

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**UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
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Researcher's Declaration

I, Akram Ullah Khan, do hereby declare on the solemn affirmation that the work presented in this article is authentic which is done under the supervision of Dr. Abdul Karim. This paper is not submitted to any other university or institution for the award of any degree, diploma or fellowship or published any time before.

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Dedication

To my father who is the ultimate role model for me.

Abstract

This research aimed to find out the factors affecting the English pronunciation of students at BS level at district Bannu. It also tried to investigate the fact that whether their local mother accent is responsible for mispronouncing some particular sounds or not. It also tried to bring out the responses of teachers while teaching pronunciation and the factors that Affect the English pronunciation of the students at BS level in Bannu. A survey was conducted in the department of English in the university of science and technology, Bannu, to find out the possible barriers that demotivate them to develop their pronunciation skills. The data of the survey was collected from both the students and the teachers and it showed the reasons that were responsible for this problem. In this connection, 50 students and 10 teachers/instructors were taken as respondents for the study. Finally, this article concluded with some solution and recommendation to overcome the pronunciation difficulties faced by the BS level students in district Bannu.

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Factors Affecting the English Pronunciation of Students at Bs level at District Bannu

Introduction

Acquiring correct pronunciation is an indispensable part of the language learning process. It plays a substantial role in enhancing the communicative competence and performance of the second language learners. The learning of correct pronunciation is a very sensitive and complicated aspect of the English language.

It is a well-known fact that a native speaker of a language can identify a non-native speaker's accent. This recognition is because of the numerous issues with the non-native speaker's accent when using a large number of consonant and vowel sounds. A second language sound system differs greatly from the mother tongue of the speaker. Foreign language speakers often mispronounce the target language, which is the reason behind the difficulties they face while communicating.

When it comes to pronunciation, English is one of the hardest languages. The lack of correlation between a word's sound and spelling in English is the root cause of this issue. Most of the time, sounds are mispronounced, which causes issues for foreign learners. Considering examples, the /r/ sound, for instance, is not pronounced at the end of words like "car," "star," etc., or when it comes after a consonant sound like "park," "dark," etc. Another illustration is the inconsistency between the pronunciation and spelling of words like knowledge, psychology, phonetics, etc. These variances make it extremely difficult for non-native English speakers to pronounce English words correctly.

It is also a well-known phenomenon that learners of English frequently excel in grammar, morphology, and semantics but fall short of getting reaching a possible level in English phonology. In this regard, mastery of the proper pronunciation of English is greatly influenced by the mother tongue interference. There are many other factors that affect the correct pronunciation which the researcher will investigate in this article.

In the current era, English is considered as the universal language of communication. Nowadays, learning English is almost mandatory particularly for the Asian nations due to its close ties with the West. Pakistan is one among those nations that are greatly influenced by the Western culture and its language.

Considering the education system, Pakistan is a way behind in reaching the required goal. Its percentage of literate citizens is poor and it ranks low among literate nations. In rural areas, the situation is particularly dire. After fourteen years of schooling, students still struggle with using the correct English language, particularly its pronunciation. In language classes that are solely beneficial to slow learners, the bilingual approach is employed. Educational institutions in Pakistan, these days, place enough focus on teaching English so that they could become more proficient in communication through reading, writing, speaking, and listening. But the most overlooked aspect of teaching is learning the correct pronunciation. Pronunciation is barely given enough weight when teaching English at the BS level in Pakistan.

The situation is even worse in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's rural areas, particularly in District Bannu where learning how to pronounce English is continuously neglected. While learning a foreign language, pronunciation is the most challenging component. Students do not have enough opportunities to practice pronunciation and the teachers often instruct students up to the BS level in Pashto or Urdu. This is the reason why students have an excessive amount of difficulty pronouncing English sounds correctly. For instance, they are unable to enunciate the /r/ sound. Most of the time, students pronounce the /r/ sound throughout a word contrary to the rules for its correct pronunciation in Received Pronunciation (RP). In a similar vein, kids tend to pronounce /f/ as /p/ because it is a non-native Pashto sound that was adopted from Arabic.

These and other similar sounds are fairly challenging for the learners to pronounce correctly. For BS English students, there is phonetics and phonology course, but for other Bs programs, there is no such course. As a result, the pronunciation of the English language is incredibly poor among the students in District Bannu. Thus, the researcher's goal was to concentrate on the investigation of factors that contribute to the incorrect pronunciation among the Students of English at BS-level in Bannu district. The researcher has attempted to draw attention to the various issues regarding English pronunciation. Moreover, the researcher has also provided some recommendations at the end.

Research Objective

- 1) To find out the causes that make the English pronunciation difficult for the students in district Bannu.
- 2) To fine out workable suggestions to overcome the problem of incorrect pronunciation.

Research Questions

- 1) what are the causes that make the English pronunciation difficult for the students at Bs level in District Bannu.
- 2) How can the problems of incorrect pronunciation be overcome.

Statement of Problem

For Pakistani English learners, it has never been easy to overcome the problem of pronunciation. Bannu is one of the remote areas where lack of opportunity further widens this issue. Teachers seldom have enough time to teach English pronunciation, and students constantly struggle with correct pronunciation. Consequently, the researcher has made an effort to identify the factors that students in Bannu district are facing while pronouncing different sounds in English.

Delimitation of the Research

It was extremely difficult for the researcher to conduct research in the whole discipline. For reliable and valid research, it was necessary to narrow down the topic to specific area. The researcher, therefore, selected Phonology as a major area and then further limited to pronunciation only. The researcher's focus was only on finding out the factors the significantly cause problems when speaking English.

Significance of the Research

This research is significant because it highlights the importance of acquiring pronunciation of the second language. Also, it provides an insight to language teachers and learners which allow them to understand the factors that affect the pronunciation of English as a second language.

The research will have a stronger impact on the students in district Bannu since it will enable them to identify the problems in their pronunciation and work out to reduce the factors that affect pronunciation. It will also be more significant for the teachers as it will help them use various techniques to help the students overcome pronunciation problems.

Literature Review

It would be ineffective to learn English if one could not be in touch properly with others in the target language. Pronunciation mistakes frequently lead to misapprehend, which disrupt communication. Therefore, learning correct pronunciation is essential for successful communication. The most notable problem faced by the pupils in English is correct pronunciation.

Pronouncing words accurately in English is a truly hard work for someone who is not native to the language. When it comes to this, English is the most difficult language. The main reason for this is that a word's spelling and pronunciation some time differ. Scholars mostly misapprehend a word's pronunciation based only on its spelling. According to Dr. Abdul Kareem, Dr. Samad and Dr. Ihsan Ullah khan (2023), Apart from the mentioned factor, there are some other factors which are necessary to be taken into consideration in reference to District Bannu. District Bannu is a poverty-stricken area. It is observed in most of the cases that students are not provided with reading materials i.e magazine, newspapers, novel and short stories etc. Such material can be exceptionally helpful in knowing the correct pronunciation. Therefore, to improve English pronunciation need a great concentration. "Pronunciation is basically known as the production of sounds that we use to produce meaning "Fact, (2002). Ur (2010) also says that pronunciation is the result of a combination of sounds, stress, rhythm, and intonation of a language.

The huge barrier which stops students from studying correct pronunciation is the absence of opportunities. Scholars from modern education systems might have the opportunity to exercise pronouncing words accurately in English, however scholars from developing regions like Bannu have many difficulties in the correct pronunciation of various sounds in English. While they may pay attention on vocabulary and grammar, they do not concentrate to practicing pronunciation. They need the resources which is beneficial to study how to pronounce words correctly. In his discussion on pronunciation mistakes, Biyaen (1997) covers the following variables. 1. Limited opportunities to utilize English in their everyday life. 2. First language interference, specifically when it comes to conversational expression and grammatical pronunciation. 3. Taking a non-active procedures to study. 4. Being very nervous to speak in English with class fellow.

Studying phonetics and phonology is crucial for the correct pronunciation. Language instruction is lacking in many developing areas, which is one of the main reasons of defective pronunciation. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, most of the teachers have the literature as major discipline. Only some teachers have mastery over English linguistics. Apart from Bs English, the course outlines do not include any specific chapters for teaching phonology and phonetics. For this reason, it can be very problematic for the pupils to study the different English sounds. Regarding the significance of phonetics and phonology, Peter Roach (2000) stated that anyone who want to know the basics of correctly using English speech sounds must have a proper knowledge of these subjects.

Due to the complex nature of English, it is beneficial to study pronunciation in terms of phonemes rather than alphabets (Roach, 2000). Teaching pronunciation is the most problematic yet essential component in teaching ESL/EFL at the same time, according to Jahan's (2011) article. She states that it is nearly tough for ESL students to obtain a faultless native-sounding accent. If skillful English speakers understand the student's pronunciation with no trouble, the communication process will be successful (Jahan, 2011). Moreover, pronunciation is necessary for speaking and listening, according to Hancock (2003). According to Momeneen (2011), scholars who have earlier earned a bachelor's degree in English are frequently reported to struggle with pronouncing words accurately, which makes them unremarkable to employers during job interviews. Additionally, they face various issues in their everyday interactions with others as a result of wrong pronunciation words (Momeneen, 2011).

This problem has some very basic reasons.

Howlader (2010) said that in the previous few years, teaching pronunciation has been ignored in EFL/ESL sites, and GTM has taken over as the basic method. Later, the Audio-lingual method adopted the traditional approach to pronunciation practice, using brief conversations and minimal pair drills (Howlader, 2010). Furthermore, the study of pronunciation has been ignored in the field of applied linguistics, according to Derwing and Munro (2005), and as a result, teachers are frequently left to depend only on their instinct with little direction. Many teachers are unwilling to teach pronunciation, even if some of them can do so well.

Gilbert quoted in Howlader (2010) declares that, although being an essential component of speaking and listening comprehension, pronunciation is entirely neglected in the course of study, teaching resources, and classroom exercises. Furthermore, Maniruzzaman (2008) states that pronunciation plays a vital role in the learning of a second or foreign language since it immediately influences the communicative competence and performance of the learner., Most teachers do not give suitable assignment to students for practice pronouncing words properly in class. The main reason is that professors normally do not have sufficient time to perform all the skills at once. Without enough practice, it is extremely difficult to attain excellent pronunciation, intonation, and highlights since conventional pronunciation needs comprehensive practice.

Speaking and listening are insolvably linked to pronunciation. But in Pakistan, especially in the more undeveloped areas, pronunciation is hardly considered when teaching and learning English at the primary and secondary levels. Trainers only concentrate on the most problematic English sounds, allowing students to make native-like sounds. However, this method is unsuccessful because foreign students are not capable to make native-like sounds. Teachers, according to Hoque (2011) only give importance to the textbook sections on reading, writing, and grammar that are necessary to pass the SSC and HSC exams. Additionally, Shuchi (2013) asserted that some teachers

may not be knowledgeable of their own English language proficiency due to a shortage of qualifications.

Students must need to know about the right function and structure of each component of English pronunciation, which is made up of various elements such as sound, stress, and variety. Furthermore, non-local speakers must carefully train their minds to pronounce words correctly and realize that bad language usage can make them irritating to both themselves and the listener. Paul Robertson (2003) suggests that practicing different areas of speech such as country-specific complex sounds, clusters, "th" sounds, and linking words and sounds would be useful for Asian scholars. Additionally, he proposed that as listener awareness is essential to pronunciation, listening evaluation, calculation, and pertinent response methods become a part of pronunciation. Resultantly, both instructors and pupils must have a necessary information of the different sounds, especially those associated with the English language.

According to Robertson (2003), the teachers should emphasize teaching pronunciation as a long-term goal and as a distinct component of spoken language. Since pronunciation is linked to reading, writing, and listening comprehension, the trainer should focus on each of these distinct areas. Accuracy should not be given much thought when the objective of the students is to increase fluency because learning both at once is very challenging. When students feel comfortable speaking, they should pay attention on accuracy since it will enable them to communicate fluently and with correct structure and manner.

Summing up the literature review, it is vivid that English, as language, carries various problems particularly considering its pronunciation. Different researchers, as discussed above, have highlighted the intricacies that are found in the pronunciation of different English sounds. Problem lies not only in the learners but also in the language as well. There are numerous issues with English language e.g the mismatch between the word spelling and its pronunciation, silencing different sounds in English and the changing pronunciation of different sounds at different places in a word. There are issues with learners as well. Different researches conducted in this discipline reveal that foreigners' students don't work on their pronunciation as is required. Moreover, teachers also don't focus on teaching pronunciation as separate skill. Even the syllabus lacks in chapters that deal with pronunciation particularly. Also, the backward areas lack in professional linguistic instructor who has good command over teaching phonetics and phonology. Thus, considering all the findings of the previous research and the issues behind incorrect pronunciation

The researcher deemed it necessary to investigate the exact problems in the pronunciation of English sounds among BS students in District Bannu and further tried to give some valuable recommendations which could help the students in making them able to speak English correctly.

Research methodology

Introduction

This portion of the research discusses the method used by the researcher for the collection and analysis of the data in District Bannu.

Mode of inquiry

The researcher in this research used quantitative methodology in order to find out the factors that affect the student's pronunciation of English at BS level and also the possible reason behind incorrect pronunciation. The research is quantitative because the researcher has used single tool for data collection. The data collected from the students as well as from teachers is presented in the form of tables.

Tool

The researcher in this research used a single tool for data collection. Questionnaire was used for both the students as well as the teachers. Moreover, the data was collected through questionnaire by adopting Lickert scale method. The researcher provided questionnaire to students, and the teachers and they were given sufficient time to tick the appropriate options. Ten different questions were asked in both the questionnaires. Before handling over questionnaire, proper instructions were given to all the students to avoid any misunderstanding in fulfilling the questionnaire.

Population

Population is the territory in which the researchers conducting his research. The researcher performs his research in the District of Bannu. Due to the difficulty of conducting research in all over the whole area, selection of a particular territory is necessary for the validity and reliability

to conduct research. It has also two extra advantages. First, it is less costly, and second, it saves the time of researcher during conducting research.

Sampling

The sample of this research is the BS level students and English teachers of English department of university of science and technology, Bannu. For this purpose, the researcher choosed fifty students and ten teachers from different semesters of English department. The students were randomly selected from 2nd, 4th, 6th, and 8th semesters. All the teachers were having qualification of master in English.

Theoretical Framework

Second language acquisition has been an area of interest for scholars and language teachers. Various scholars have attempted to resolve the problems that hamper the learning efficiency. In this regard Stephen Krashan's monitor Model is a theory of second language acquisition that consists of five main hypotheses:

1) the Acquisition-Learning Hypothesis

Acquisition is an unconscious procedure similar to how offspring memorize their native language.

Learning is an intentional procedure including traditional instruction and awareness about the language (grammar rules).

2) The Monitor Hypothesis

The Monitor is a psychological editor that uses learned information to correct language use.

It only works when there is time to think about rules, the speaker is concentrating on body, and they be familiar with the rules.

3) The Natural Order Hypothesis

Language learners develop language structures in a foreseeable order.

This sequence is not necessarily the same as the order in which language is taught.

4) The Input Hypothesis

Learners develop language by understanding input that is slightly beyond their current level of competence ($i+1$).

Intelligible input is important for language acquisition.

5) The Affective Filter Hypothesis

Emotional variables such as motivation, self-confidence, and anxiety affect language acquisition.

A high affective filter (e.g., high anxiety) can hinder language acquisition by blocking comprehensible input.

Similarly, Schumaun has profounded the theory of Acculturation.

An acculturation model is a theoretical framework that describes how individuals or groups adjust and adapt to a new cultural environment. It explores the processes and outcomes of cultural change when different cultures come into direct contact.

Key components of acculturation models typically include

Integration: Individuals maintain their original cultural identity while also adopting aspects of the new culture.

Assimilation: Individuals fully adopt the new culture and lose their original cultural identity.

Separation: Individuals maintain their original culture and reject the new culture.

Marginalization: Individuals lose their original culture without fully adopting the new culture, leading to a sense of disconnection from both cultures.

One of the most well-known acculturation models is John Berry's model, which categorizes the acculturation strategies into the four types mentioned above. This model helps in understanding the complexities of cultural adaptation and the factors that influence successful acculturation, such as social support, cultural similarities, and individual characteristics.

Moreover, Accommodation theory, developed by Howard Giles in the 1970s, explores how individuals adjust their communication styles to either converge with or diverge from their interlocutors. The theory suggests that people adapt their speech, gestures, and other communication behaviors based on social identity and interpersonal goals.

Convergence: This involves adopting similar communication styles to reduce social distance, increase rapport, and gain approval. For example, a person might mimic the accent or speaking speed of someone they admire or wish to connect with.

Divergence: This entails emphasizing differences in communication to maintain social distance or assert identity. For instance, someone might use their native dialect more strongly when interacting with someone from a different cultural background to highlight their distinctiveness.

Accommodation theory is used to understand dynamics in various contexts, such as intercultural communication, workplace interactions, and social relationships. It highlights the role of language and behavior in managing social relationships and identities.

Keeping in view the theories of SLA, the researcher has attempted to find out the causes for bad pronunciation of English among the students of English at District Bannu.

Data collection and analysis

In this chapter, the researcher has analyzed the data collected from the learners and teachers. All the participants were from the department of English in the University of Science and Technology Bannu. The researcher has used single tool for both the students as well as the teachers and the data are analyzed in mathematical form and then presented in descriptive form.

The data collected from the learners as well as from teachers is presented in table form. Separate questions were asked from the learners as well as from the teachers. All the questions were close ended.

The data collected from the learners is presented in table form which is given below.

Questions	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Dis Agree	Strongly Dis Agree
1. Students at BS level in District Bannu face many difficulties in the correct pronunciation of English sound.	13(25%)	37(75%)	0%	0%	0%
2. The activities being used in classes to learn English would help the students to overcome pronunciation difficulties.	15(30%)	25(50%)	5(10%)	05(10%)	0%
3. There is enough time given in classroom to work on pronunciation skill.	5(10%)	0%	15(30%)	30(60%)	0%
4. The students use Pashto accent while speaking English.	25(50%)	20(40%)	5(10%)	0%	0%
5. Some of the students often pronounce /p/ as /f/.	25(50%)	25(50%)	15(30%)	5(10%)	0%
6. Some of the students pronounce /t/ incorrectly because of the mother tongue interference.	22(45%)	8(15%)	10(20%)	10(20%)	0%
7. Students, most often, pronounce the /r/ sounds incorrectly.	25(50%)	20(40%)	0%	5(10%)	0%
8. There are particular chapter in syllabus to practice pronunciation.	8(15%)	7(15%)	10(20%)	25(50%)	0%
9. Students do not get enough opportunity to practice speaking inside the classroom.	27(55%)	20(40%)	0%	3(5%)	0%
10. Opportunity to listen to native speakers on the screen is given.	5(10%)	3(5%)	7(15%)	18(35%)	17(35%)

In response to the first question, 37(75%) students Strongly agreed that students at BS level in District Bannu face many difficulties in the correct pronunciation of English sounds while 13(25%) students marked the option agree. It indicates that almost all the learners face difficulties in the correct pronunciation of English sounds.

In response to the second question, 15(30%) students agreed that the activities being used in classes to learn English would help the students to overcome pronunciation difficulties. While 25(50%) students strongly agreed. However, 5(10%) students disagree to this while 5(10%) remained neutral. The data collected regarding this question show that the activities already used in classrooms are helpful enough to overcome the pronunciation problems. However, it needs to be further enhanced so that the problem of pronunciation may be solved altogether.

Answering the third question, 30(60%) students disagreed and that there is not enough time given in classrooms to work on pronunciation skill. 5(10%) students agreed to this while 15(30%) became neutral. Majority of the learners were of the opinion that the classroom time is not enough to solve the problems of pronunciation.

Similarly, in response to the fourth question 25(50%) students were agreed that the students use Pashto accent while speaking English. 20(40%) students strongly agreed with this while 5(10%) students became neutral. Thus, it is very obvious that mother tongue strongly interferes while speaking the target language.

While answering the fifth question, 25(50%) students agreed that some of the students often pronounce /p/ as /f/. 5(10%) students strongly agreed with this while 5(10%) students disagreed with this. And 15(30%) students became neutral. Thus, here is a vivid example of incorrect pronunciation among the students. The reason is obvious; it yet again indicates that mother tongue interferes while speaking second language.

In reply to the sixth question, 22(45%) students agreed that some of the students pronounce /t/ incorrectly because of the mother tongue interference while 8(15%) students strongly agreed with this. 10(20%) students disagreed with this while 10(20%) students became neutral.

On responding to question seven, 25(50%) students agreed that students, most often pronounce the /r/ sounds incorrectly and 20(40%) students Strongly agreed with this. While 5(10%) students

disagreed with this. /r/ is one of the most problematic sounds considering its pronunciation rules; thus, majority of the students face problems in the correct pronunciation of this particular sound.

In response to the eighth question, 25(50%) students disagreed that there are particular chapters in syllabus to practice pronunciation and 10(20%) students were became neutral. 8(15%) students agreed that there are particular chapter in syllabus to practice pronunciation while 7(15%) students Strongly agreed to this. The data collected from the students regarding this question indicate that although there may be some exercises regarding pronunciation practices, there are no separate chapter in the syllabus which are based on teaching pronunciation.

Answering the ninth question, 27(55%) students agreed that students do not get enough opportunity to practice speaking inside the classroom while 20(40%) students Strongly agreed to this. Only 3(5%) students were disagreeing to this. Thus, lack of opportunity to practice pronunciation is one of the major reasons of lacking pronunciation skills.

And finally, in response to the tenth question, 18(35%) students disagreed that opportunity of listening to the native speakers on the screen is provided while 17(35%) students Strongly disagreed to this and 7(15%) students remained neutral. 5(10%) students agreed that opportunity to listen to native speakers on the screen is given while only 3(5%) students Strongly agreed to this. So, it indicates that listening opportunity is also not provided to the students learning English language.

The data collected from the teachers is presented in table form which is given below.

Questions	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Dis Agree	Strongly Dis Agree
1. Phonology was included as subject in my BS/MA degree program.	4(40%)	0%	2(20%)	4(40%)	0%
2. I got proper command over phonology during my BS/MA degree.	2(20%)	0%	8(80%)	0%	0%
3. Learning the correct pronunciation is one of the most difficult aspects in phonology.	8(80%)	0%	2(20%)	0%	0%
4. I can easily differentiate between British and American accents.	8(80%)	2(20%)	0%	0%	0%
5. Mother tongue interference is the biggest problem in learning the correct pronunciation of English.	6(60%)	2(20%)	0%	2(20%)	0%
6. During my class, I can find extra time to work on students' pronunciation skills.	4(40%)	0%	2(20%)	2(20%)	2(20%)
7. I use digital devices to help the students in improving Their pronunciation.	6(60%)	2(20%)	0%	0%	2(20%)
8. Most of the time, students are less interested in enhancing their Pronunciation Skills.	0%	6(60%)	2(20%)	0%	2(20%)
9. Lack of confidence is one of the major reasons of the poor pronunciation among the students in District Bannu.	4(40%)	4(40%)	0%	2(20%)	0%
10. I teach phonetics and Phonology as a separate subject to my students.	2(20%)	2(20%)	0%	6(60%)	0%

In response to the first question, 4(40%) teachers agreed that phonology was included as subject in my BS/MA degree while 2(20%) teachers marked the option neutral. While 4(40%) teachers disagreed with it. It is evident from the data collected in this particular chapter that majority of the teacher did not learn phonology during their academic career. It is obviously a major concern about learning the correct pronunciation by the students in District Bannu.

In response to the second question, 8(80%) teachers marked neutral option about getting proper command over phonology during their BS/MA degree. While 2(20%) teachers agreed to this. Thus, mostly the teachers of English do not know in depth about phonology.

Answering the third question, 8(80%) teachers agreed that learning the correct pronunciation is one of the most difficult aspects in phonology. While 2(20) % teachers were marked the neutral

option. The data reveal that learning the correct pronunciation is one of the major challenges in English language.

Similarly, in response to the fourth question 8(80%) teachers agreed that they can easily differentiate between British and American accents. 2(20%) teachers strongly agreed with this. Knowing the intricate differences between the two major accents I.e. American and British is very important for correct and fluent English. The collected data show that mostly the teachers are well aware about the differences in the above-mentioned accents.

Answering the fifth question, 6(60%) teachers agreed that mother tongue interference is the biggest problem in learning the correct pronunciation of English while 2(20%) teachers strongly agreed with this and 2(20%) teachers disagreed with this. It is very obvious that the mother tongue of the learners interferes to great extent while learning a second language and the data also confirm this notion.

In reply to the sixth question, 4(40%) teachers agreed that during their classes, they can find extra time to work on students' pronunciation skills. while 2 (20%) teachers were marked the neutral option. 2(20%) teachers disagreed with this while 2(20%) teachers Strongly disagreed to this. So, the class time needs to be extended to work out on the pronunciation problems.

On responding to question seven, 6(60%) teachers agreed that they use digital devices to help the students in improving their pronunciation while 2 (20%) teachers Strongly agreed with this. And 2(20%) teachers Strongly disagreed with this.

In response to the eighth question, 6(60%) teachers Strongly agreed that most of the time, students are less interested in enhancing Their pronunciation skills. and 2(20%) teachers were marked the neutral option. While 2(20%) teachers Strongly disagreed. Learner's interest is very necessary for overcoming the problem of pronunciation however, the data show that most of the students do not take much interest in solving the issue of incorrect pronunciation.

Answering the ninth question, 4(40%) teachers agreed that lack of the confidence is one of the major reasons of the poor pronunciation among the students in District Bannu while 4(40%) teachers Strongly agreed to this. Only 2(20%) teachers disagreed to this.

And finally, in response to the tenth question, 6(60%) teachers disagreed that they can teach Phonetics as a separate subject to their students. While 2(20%) teachers agreed and that they can teach Phonetics as a separate subject and 2(20%) teachers Strongly agreed to this. Thus again, it is clear from the response of the teachers that teaching phonetics is difficult for them and hence, this is one of the major hurdles in learning the correct pronunciation of English.

CONCLUSION

Summary of the Findings

The research was about to find out the factors that Affects the English Pronunciation of students at BS level at district Bannu. The researcher has collected data from the teachers and students in the department of English and applied linguistics in university of science and technology Bannu. In this research, 10 teachers and 50 students take participated. The data were collected in form of questionnaire from both. It is found from the research that the learners in district Bannu face many problems in the pronunciation of English sounds. It has cleared from the research that the learners have no opportunity for enhancing pronunciation. The research also points out the main reasons of that difficulty. The teachers have less time to help the learners in this issue. Mother tongue interferes to very high extent which creates difficulties for the students. Moreover, learners are less serious to overcome this problem. Also, there is insufficient facilities for the learners as well as for the teachers. So, the students' pronunciation is very poor in this region.

Practical Implications

It is expected that this research would be useful for the teachers as well as for the learners and they will take advantage of the research later on. The knowledge in this research can be used in the classroom for their improvement and it would provide an opportunity for them to overcome the pronunciation difficulties. This study has also shown the poor education system in this region and thus it would help the concern authorities to take some essential steps in order to make better the education system in Bannu.

Major causes

The concentration of the researcher was to discover the various difficulties and causes faced by the learners in the correct pronunciation of English. Below are some of the major causes of pronunciation issues. All the causes are based on the data collected from the teachers and learners.

1. The biggest issue of the learners is the first language interference. Most of the professors agreed on this problem. In most of the English words, learners include their native language sounds and thus they pronounce the words incorrectly.

/r/, /f/, /p/ and /t/ sound are very prominent in Pashto language and that is why most of the learners mix them with English sounds system. Pashto accent also interferes while speaking English which makes the pronunciation irritating and it becomes hard for the Pashto talkers to interact with foreigners in English.

2. It is clear from the collected data that one of the big reasons of poor pronunciation is the learners' lack of interest. Majority of the learners consider it non beneficial to practice pronunciation. They give proper time to other activities like learning grammar and vocabulary but completely neglected the proper pronunciation. Teachers also do not stress on the significance of correct pronunciation. Furthermore, only some learners take advantage of digital dictionaries and other applications for this purpose.

3. Another cause for the pronunciation issue is that, in this region, the education standard is extremely low. Secondly, there is also political interference in every educational institute due to which most of the learners do not attend their classes regularly and properly. They completely neglect their studies and thus it leads to students' failure. They do not disturb themselves to study their given course outlines, how will they concentrate on this extra activity.

4. Majority of the teachers responded that there is insufficient time for the teachers to practice pronunciation and teach the students about phonetics and phonology.

5. Most of the teachers use their native language while teaching in the classrooms. Though the teachers did not mention this reason in the collected data but it is our personal experience about the teaching in this area. There is very little communication in English. If the teachers use their native language for teaching, how will the learners communicate in English and if they do not communicate in English, they will not be able to defeat this problem.

6. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, all the teachers at the Department of English may not have mastered English phonology, as it was not included in their course when they were students, though phonology is now part of the English programme.

7. Internet plays very important role in overcoming pronunciation issues. There are applications which can be used only through internet. There are also online lectures available on phonetics and phonology which is of high value for the learners to learn proper English. But the internet connection is very poor in District Bannu. The internet facility is often not good in colleges and

universities for the students and thus the learners cannot access to internet easily. Watching English films, different documentaries and listening to English songs are very effective in learning correct pronunciation. But due to lack of internet facility, the learners do not take interest in watching and listening them and that is why they are far behind in speaking correct English.

These are some of the basic causes and difficulties pointed out by the researcher. All these causes are based on the data collected from both teachers and student's questionnaire.

Suggestions and Recommendations

This research revealed some significant information about the pronunciation difficulties in district Bannu. So, at the end the researcher would like to give some suggestions and recommendation for the improvements of students' pronunciation of English.

According to the research, native language interference is the biggest problem. To get suitable solution of the problem, teachers should guide their students and mentor them on the laws governing various English sounds, specifically those that are same to Pashto English. There is insufficient time in class for the teachers to help the students and go over pronunciation practices. In order to facilitate the learners, the professor needs to be provided sufficient time for this purpose. It is better to assign one or two courses per week entirety for pronunciation practices.

The problems of pronunciation in classes must be analyze by using English only for communication. The teachers should also motivate the learners to practice English for communication outside the classes. Speaking English with relatives and companions might help learners become a better speaker of the language. For their developments, the learners need to watch movies and documentaries in English. Speaking correct English want a great concentration on listening. Furthermore, being quite entertaining, watching movies and other documentaries can help learners pronounce words accurately and with the right accent. Additionally, as electronic dictionaries are readily available on every mobile phone, learners must need to use them. They should make use of many internet resources, such as listening to lectures on phonology and phonetics, playing games online that practice pronouncing words correctly, and so on.

These are some of the ideas and recommendations made by the researcher, and it would be advantageous if they followed them.

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Appendix

Questionnaire for Data Collection from students

TOPIC: Factors Affecting the English pronunciation of students at Bs level in District Bannu

Assalam-O-Alaikum, I am going to conduct research for my BS program. This is a research-based questionnaire for the BS students of Bannu. You are requested to fill it, as it will help the researcher to find out the factors that affect the English pronunciation of BS level students. Thanks

Name _____ Education _____ Department _____

Tick the appropriate option. Your own opinion and suggestions would be highly appreciated.

1. Students at BS level in District Bannu face many difficulties in the correct pronunciation of English sound.

(1) Agree (2) Strongly agree (3) Neutral (4) Disagree (5) Strongly disagree

2) The activities being used in classes to learn English would help the students to overcome pronunciation difficulties.

3) There is enough time given in classroom to work on pronunciation skill.

4) The students use Pashto accent while speaking English.

5) Some of the students often pronounce /p/ as /f/.

6) Some of the students pronounce /t/ incorrectly because of the mother tongue interference.

7) Students, most often, pronounce the /r/ sounds incorrectly.

8) There are particular chapter in syllabus to practice pronunciation.

9) Students do not get enough opportunity to practice speaking inside the classroom.

10) Opportunity to listen to native speakers on the screen is given.

Questionnaire for Data Collection from Teachers

Topic: Factors Affecting the English pronunciation of the students at Bs level at District Bannu

Assalam-O-Alaikum, I am going to conduct research for my BS program. This is a research-based questionnaire for Teachers. You are requested to fill it, as it will help the researcher to find out the factors that affect the English pronunciation of BS level students. Thanks

Name _____ Qualification _____ Department _____

Tick the appropriate option. Your own opinion and suggestions would be highly appreciated.

1. Phonology was included as subject in my BS/MA degree program.

1) Agree 2) Strongly agree 3) Neutral 4) Disagree 5) Strongly disagree.

2. I got proper command over phonology during my BS/MA degree.

3. Learning the correct pronunciation is one of the most difficult aspects in phonology.

4. I can easily differentiate between British and American accents.

5. Mother tongue interference is the biggest problem in learning the correct pronunciation of English.

6. During my class, I can find extra time to work on students' pronunciation skills.

7. I use digital devices to help the students in improving Their pronunciation.

8. Most of the time, students are less interested in enhancing their Pronunciation Skills.

9. Lack of confidence is one of the major reasons of the poor pronunciation among the students in District Bannu.

10. I teach phonetics and Phonology as a separate subject to my students.